

Structure and properties analysis by the Associate Solutions Thermodynamic Model in BaO-P₂O₅ glasses

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ABSTRACT

Disclosing of composition-structure-property relationship in various glasses either by experimental techniques and/or theoretical models has significant research in the glass science since couple of decades. Rather than studying using highly sophisticated experimental tools, such as solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS), and neutron diffraction analysis etc., the thermodynamic model of associate solutions (SVTDM) has grab our attention to study the structure of the glasses, especially phosphate glasses. This model was developed in glasses by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva [1], and applied to silicate, borate, phosphate and chalcogenide glasses to predict their structure. Moreover, the model applicability has been verified by comparing the predicted structure with the structure studied experimentally and predicted physical parameters value with measured value.

As we knew that, phosphate glasses possess remarkable functional properties such as low viscosity, high refractive indices, lower melting temperature as compared to silicate and borate glasses, high thermal expansion coefficient and the high transparency in the ultraviolet range which make them excellent candidates for glass to metal sealing applications, vitrification of radioactive waste and photonics [2, 3]. So that studying the structure of binary barium phosphate glasses through the SVTD model has worthwhile.

The main objective of this work is that study the structure of BaO-P₂O₅ glasses through the SVTD model and verification of its applicability by study the structure experimentally through the MAS-NMR analysis. Furthermore, the physical and thermodynamic properties of the glasses against BaO content will be evaluated.

In order to study the structure experimentally glass samples with chemical composition (100-x) P₂O₅-x BaO, where x = 40, 42.5, 45, 47.5, 50, 52.5, 55, and 57.5 mol% were prepared using melt and quenching technique. These glasses hereafter labeled as 40_BaO, 42.5_BaO, 45_BaO, 47.5_BaO, 50_BaO, 52.5_BaO, 55_BaO and 57.5_BaO for the respective 40, 42.5, 45, 47.5, 50, 52.5, 55 and 57.5 mol% of BaO content.

SVTD Model for BaO-P₂O₅ glasses

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

In order to construct the thermodynamic model, we computed equilibrium molar amounts and molar fractions of the input components (stable crystalline components that have identified through the phase diagram [4] and systems components) from corresponding Gibbs energies taken from the FACT data base (except B3P2 phase) at different temperatures, 300 and 1000 K. The equilibrium molar amounts of input components against BaO content represents the SVTD model, depicted in Fig. 1 for BaO-P₂O₅ glasses. Two pseudo-regions i.e. (i), binary ($0 \leq x \leq 0.33$) and (ii) ternary ($0.33 \leq x \leq 0.60$) regions have been observed in the glass forming region (< 60 mol% BaO). The tetrahedral units Qⁿ (n= 0, 1, 2, and 3) that are presented in the glasses were calculated based on equilibrium molar fraction of the input components and their variation against BaO content illustrated in Fig. 2. For selected glasses, theoretical and analyzed composition and predicted tetrahedral units Q³, Q² and Q¹ from the model and the MAS-NMR analysis are tabulated in the following table 1. Furthermore, the molar volume (V_M) of the investigated glasses was predicted through the model based on the molar volume of input components and has coincide with the measured value with maximum error (≤ 6 %).

Table 1: Theoretical and analyzed compositions in mol%, and Qⁿ (n= 0, 1, 2, and 3) tetrahedral units obtained from the model and MAS-NMR analysis against BaO content for selected glasses.

Glass	Theoretical		Analyzed			SVTD Model (in %)			MAS-NMR (in %)		
	P ₂ O ₅	BaO	P ₂ O ₅	BaO	Al ₂ O ₃	Q ³	Q ²	Q ¹	Q ³	Q ²	Q ¹
42.5_BaO	57.5	42.5	56.42	41.53	2.05	27	72	1	21	79	0
45_BaO	55.0	45.0	54.57	44.17	1.23	21	76	3	17	83	0
50_BaO	50.0	50.0	49.87	48.85	1.24	10	80	10	10	84	6
52.5_BaO	47.5	52.5	47.13	51.84	1.40	5	79	16	5	72	23
55_BaO	45.0	55.0	45.87	53.40	0.72	2	74	24	0	72	28

Keywords: Barium Phosphate glasses; SVTD Model; Structure; MAS-NMR; Viscosity of liquid flow;

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